

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Empowering Beyond 5G Networks: An Experimental Assessment of Zero-Touch Management and Orchestration

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This work was supported in part by the H2020 Distributed management of Network Slices in beyond 5G (MonB5G) Project under Grant 871780; in part by Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO)–Program Programa de Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión I+D (UNICO I+D) under Grant TSI-063000-2021-54 and Grant TSI-063000-2021-55; in part by the “ERDF—A way of making Europe” project funded by Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación/Agencia Estatal de Investigación (MCIN/AEI)/10.13039/501100011033 under Grant PID2021-126431OB-I00, Grant MINECO TSI-064100-2022-16, and Grant TSI-064100-2023-26; and in part by the Generalitat de Catalunya under Grant 2021 SGR 00770.

ABSTRACT Effective zero-touch management and orchestration (ZSM&O) is crucial for scaling network slicing, particularly transitioning toward Beyond 5G (B5G) and 6G networks. This paper empirically validates the network slicing framework developed under the European Union Horizon 2020 MonB5G project. Building on three years of academia-industry collaboration, MonB5G introduces a flexible slicing model featuring umbrella slices that orchestrate modular, specialized slices across multi-domain environments to address next-generation service demands. For the first time, we evaluate its practicality in a 5G cloud-native testbed through a virtual reality (VR) streaming use case, supported by solutions such as federated learning-based CPU forecasting, anomaly detection, and deep reinforcement learning (DRL) for radio access network (RAN) optimization. The paper offers insights from technically demanding experimental tests and highlights challenges and development paths for managing next-generation mobile networks.

INDEX TERMS Network slicing, scalability, network management, orchestration, B5G, testbed.

I. INTRODUCTION

Network slicing has emerged as a fundamental concept in modern telecommunications, allowing the creation of multiple virtualized, independent networks over a shared physical

The associate editor coordinating the review of this manuscript and approving it for publication was Guangjie Han¹.

infrastructure, each tailored to meet the specific requirements of diverse use cases [1]. As the industry advances Beyond 5G (B5G) and 6G, the effective management of these network slices is becoming increasingly critical, particularly for the dynamic orchestration and optimization of network resources. To handle the growing complexity of this task, automation driven by Artificial Intelligence (AI)-enhanced

data mechanisms is indispensable, enabling real-time adaptations to the diverse and evolving demands of each slice [2]. Additionally, integrating cloud-native architectures optimizes resource allocation by facilitating the efficient deployment of network functions (NFs) as microservices, further enhancing scalability and operational agility [3].

Efforts to enable zero-touch management and orchestration (ZSM&O) focus on reducing human intervention by automating configuration, healing, optimization, and protection (CHOP) tasks using AI [4]. Standardization bodies like ITU-T, 3GPP, and ETSI's ZSM [5], [6], [7] are working to establish frameworks that integrate these capabilities. Meanwhile, open-source initiatives such as the Open Network Automation Platform and the O-RAN Alliance [8] continue to drive practical implementations of these innovations.

Capitalizing on these advancements, the MonB5G framework, a Horizon 2020 project building on three years of academia-industry collaboration, introduces an AI-driven management architecture designed to address the complexities of future 6G networks [9]. The framework employs a modular and distributed approach to management and orchestration (M&O), effectively leveraging AI to automate operational tasks with a strong emphasis on reducing energy consumption. Additionally, it facilitates real-time, end-to-end monitoring through a metric-gathering system that integrates novel key performance indicators (KPIs) tailored for slice management [10]. MonB5G further distinguishes itself through its decentralized orchestration of network slices. Inspired by ETSI's ZSM architecture, the framework utilizes a separation of concerns strategy that enhances resource allocation and operational efficiency.

While the MonB5G framework demonstrated significant potential in theory [9], [10], a gap exists between conceptual design and practical implementation. To address this, we experimentally validate the MonB5G framework in a cloud-native 5G network testbed, aiming to provide practical insights derived from this real-world implementation. Specifically, we assess a VR streaming use case which decomposes the VR *umbrella* slice into three interrelated components (or *support* slices), each with dedicated monitoring and management capabilities. In summary, this paper makes three key contributions: *i*) showcasing the deployment of the MonB5G framework in a cloud-native 5G testbed, *ii*) integrating AI-based automation for managing network slices in a VR use case, and *iii*) contributing to the 6G roadmap by highlighting challenges and development paths for managing next-generation mobile networks.

II. RELATED WORK

The field of Zero-touch network Service Management (ZSM) and slice orchestration in 5G and emerging 6G networks is rapidly evolving, focusing on improving automation, resource allocation and dynamic adaptation of network slices to meet evolving requirements. The concept of ZSM revolves around network management automation and aims

to minimize human intervention in operational processes, thus improving network efficiency and flexibility. Given the rapid development in this area, recent works have highlighted the importance of standardization efforts and advanced orchestration mechanisms to achieve full automation. Rodriguez-Vivas et al. [11] explore usig autonomic control loops and automated planning in network slice reconfiguration, focusing on tenant-oriented configurations that allow for greater adaptability in managing network slices. Another recent work by Dalgitsis et al. [12] introduces a cloud-native orchestration framework that federates network slices across different administrative domains, a key consideration in 5G/6G environments for ensuring seamless service delivery. Camargo et al. [13] take a machine learning approach to dynamically reconfigure slices in virtualized 5G networks by forecasting computational capacity, emphasizing the potential of AI/ML techniques in enhancing the flexibility and efficiency of slice orchestration. These works complement standardization efforts led by bodies like ETSI ZSM [14] and Experiential Network Intelligence (ENI) [15], which provide frameworks and specifications for zero-touch service management and network slice orchestration in 5G and beyond. The ETSI ZSM framework emphasizes the need for automated closed-loop processes and cross-domain orchestration to facilitate ZSM deployment. Furthermore, the ENI group is exploring AI-driven network management solutions, which align with the need for intelligent orchestration in future networks.

Additional recent research has explored various angles of slice orchestration. For example, Salhab et al. [16] investigate deep reinforcement learning-based orchestration strategies for dynamic slice resource allocation in heterogeneous 5G environments. Regarding policy and closed-loop control, Celdan et al. [17] introduce a policy-based framework for managing network slices in mobile communication systems to achieve efficient, flexible, and dynamic network slice management. Bega et al. [1] present a study on AI-based orchestration mechanisms to optimize network slice management, which includes resource allocation, performance optimization, and the automation of slice lifecycle operations. The scalability of ZSM and its implications for orchestration have also been a subject of active research. Afolabi et al. [18] focus on scalable orchestration mechanisms that support network slicing in large-scale deployments and across various network segments (e.g., radio access network, core network, and transport network) to support the diverse and stringent requirements of 5G services. Furthermore, Esmaeily et al. [19] present a testbed designed to evaluate and implement network slicing in 4G/5G environments using Software Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) technologies. The testbed provides a cloud-based environment for exploring the practical deployment and orchestration of end-to-end (E2E) network slices.

From an architectural perspective, Kuklinski et al. [20] propose a novel framework, named 6G-LEGO, designed to enable flexible and efficient network slicing for future

6G networks. The framework aims to address the unique requirements of 6G by providing advanced mechanisms for slice creation, management, and orchestration, drawing on the experiences and challenges identified in 5G networks. Papadakis et al. [21] explore the use of blockchain technology for orchestrating network slices, specifically to facilitate cross-slice communication at the network edge and address the challenge of managing network slices that need to interoperate while maintaining security, privacy, and efficiency. Other works, like that of Singh et al. [22] address the challenge of energy-efficient management and orchestration in large-scale 5G Radio Access Network (RAN). The paper focuses on developing strategies to reduce energy consumption in metro-scale 5G deployments while maintaining high network performance and meeting Quality of Service (QoS) requirements. Abbas et al. [23] propose a novel approach for managing and orchestrating network slices using advanced analytics driven by ensemble learning techniques.

While the above studies have significantly contributed to ZSM and network slicing, many remain conceptual, simulation-based, or focused on specific challenges like policy management, AI-driven optimization, or cross-domain federation. Our work stands apart by providing practical insights from real-world 5G deployments. Specifically, we apply the MonB5G framework to a VR video streaming use case, where the network slice is concretely defined and subdivided into interrelated slices that manage both physical parameters and service-specific characteristics. This integrated system of monitoring, analytics, and decision-making operationalizes network slicing, addressing a gap in the literature where slicing is often treated as an abstract concept. Drawing on three years of collaboration between academia and industry, this paper offers lessons learned from tangible 5G deployments and outlines a roadmap toward advancing 6G.

III. NETWORK SLICE MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK

A. FRAMEWORK ARCHITECTURE

The design philosophy of the MonB5G framework is to provide a hierarchical feedback loop-based control for Fault, Configuration, Accounting, Performance and Security (FCAPS) management, together with slice orchestration at different scopes, goals, and time scales [10]. The management hierarchy includes the global Operational Support System (OSS)/Business Support System (BSS) level, the technological domain level, the slice level, and the node level. Figure 1 shows the architectural vision of MonB5G on the left side, the framework itself – as described next – in the middle, and the associated goals towards B5G/6G on the right side [9], [24].

The MonB5G framework consists of a multi-layer architecture that bridges the gap between the high-level orchestration and the underlying network infrastructure. There are various domains at the infrastructure layer (technology,

administrative, network elements, and network slices). This layer is responsible for the physical and virtual resources on which the network is based. Each domain — whether cloud infrastructure, edge or RAN — can perform its own monitoring, analysis, and decision-making functions. The network elements within each domain execute control loops via Embedded Element Managers (EEMs).

The management and orchestration layer is at the heart of the MonB5G framework, where orchestration tasks are distributed between the Domain Manager and Orchestrators (DMOs) and the Inter-Domain Manager and Orchestrator (IDMO). The DMOs manage individual domains autonomously and make localized decisions, while the IDMO oversees coordination across multiple DMOs and ensures coherent policy enforcement and network-wide slice management. This hierarchical structure supports scalability as each DMO can perform slice management tasks locally while the IDMO maintains overarching control and coordination.

In the M&O layer, the IDMO is responsible for modifying the end-to-end slice template before it is deployed according to the negotiated contract and interacts with the DMOs to deploy the end-to-end slices based on the information received from the DMOs, which is responsible for orchestrating slices in its domain and managing its corresponding resources. One of the key features of the MonB5G architecture is its flexible and modular design, which allows each DMO and IDMO to interact seamlessly. This is achieved through standard interfaces that facilitate data exchange and control operations. Communication between these entities takes place via APIs that support domain-specific requirements, ensuring consistency and coherence of slice operations across different domains. The architecture's interaction model is designed to be adaptable and promote interoperability between DMOs within their local domains and with the IDMO for higher-level policy coordination.

Within each DMO, the architecture comprises four key components — Monitoring System (MS), Analytical Engine (AE), Decision Engine (DE), and Actuator (ACT) - that work together to enable intelligent orchestration. The MS plays a central role in collecting real-time data from network elements and uses various protocols or APIs to effectively monitor performance and operational metrics. The AE analyses the data using AI and federated learning techniques to predict resource requirements, detect anomalies, and assess network behaviour to ensure proactive and data-driven orchestration. Insights from AE feed into DE, which makes informed decisions to manage the network slice. By using AI-based decision algorithms, such as multi-agent reinforcement learning, the DE ensures optimal resource allocation and network configuration. The ACT then implements these decisions by communicating with the infrastructure layer to perform resource adjustments, slice reconfigurations or other necessary actions and connect the orchestration layer to the underlying network components.

On the other hand, there are several domains in the infrastructure layer, including technology, administrative,

FIGURE 1. The MonB5G vision, framework, and goals for achieving zero-touch networks in 6G.

network elements, and network slices. Each technology domain (e.g., cloud infrastructure, edge, or RAN) can run its own instances of monitoring, analysis, and decision-making functions. At each network element layer, the control loops are implemented as part of a modified Element Manager (EM), called EEM. Whether deployed statically or dynamically, all components of the architecture belong to MS, AE, DE, and ACT sublayers.

As described later, the slices discussed and experimented in Section IV fit into DMOs with their corresponding sublayers. Remarkably, a relevant target of the framework is to solve the problem of network slice management scalability, i.e., a scalable system to manage a massive number of coexisting network slices with different technical requirements. In this regard, the MS, AE, DE, and ACT are developed in a distributed and programmable manner. AI-powered management operations are distributed as well to different levels of the management hierarchy, providing significant complexity reduction and rapid analysis of slices. Unlike centralized management systems, the monitoring and analytics capabilities of the proposed management platform are embedded locally as part of the slices with AI-driven enablers to achieve high scalability, especially for slices spanning multiple domains.

The MonB5G framework is inherently modular, extensible, and designed to integrate with existing systems like NFV MANO, enhancing them with AI-driven automation and analytics. This adds intelligence to resource management, enabling more agile, autonomous orchestration of network functions. MonB5G extends NFV MANO with proactive decision-making for rapid adjustments to network conditions and service demands. Its interfaces ensure seamless communication with heterogeneous network elements, regardless of technology or vendor.

B. A SCALABLE AND ROBUST MONITORING SYSTEM

The MS is a central component used to collect detailed information about the current state of the elements supporting the network slices, often deployed in multiple domains [25]. As shown in Figure 2, Sampling Functions (SFs) are responsible for requesting data from the EEMs and publishing it on a Kafka bus. More specifically, an SF implements the sampling loop operations, triggering an API to collect metrics at a specified interval and then passing the data to the streaming bus. To enable real-time monitoring for online analysis of slice KPIs and reconfiguration in response to dynamic network conditions, scalability of the MS is crucial for managing a large number of slices. To achieve this, the framework employs three main approaches.

The first approach to achieving scalability in the MS is through its distributed design. The MS is built on a microservice architecture and implemented as a cloud-native application in a Kubernetes cluster, allowing it to leverage Kubernetes’ automatic scaling features. Specifically, the resources of the MS can dynamically adjust to varying workloads by defining auto-scaling rules in the Kubernetes deployment.

The second approach involves the hierarchical structure of the MS, which is designed in a modular and layered way. In this design, a MS can act as either a data source or a consumer of data from another MS, referred to as a *parent MS* and *child MS*, respectively. More specifically, the parent MS can aggregate data from one or more child MSs, while a child MS serves as a local monitoring instance that collects and pre-processes data before passing it to the parent MS. This hierarchical system enables monitoring and data (pre)processing tasks to be performed at lower levels, reducing traffic and improving reaction times. Data collected by the child MSs is aggregated by the parent MS

FIGURE 3. Multi-site cloud-native 5G experimental testbed setup and deployed solutions.

with its own MS, AE, DE, and ACT, which operate together to ensure the efficient and dynamic management of the slice. An example of this approach is presented later in Section IV and illustrated in Figure 4, where the umbrella slice oversees the lifecycle of supporting slices, each with distinct roles in delivering the desired VR service.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND MONB5G SLICES

Figure 3 provides an overview of the experimental setup used for all the slices presented in this paper. The infrastructure spans three distinct physical sites, each running its own independent Kubernetes cluster, with each site hosting an instance of the MS and one or various AEs, DEs, and ACTs. Two of these sites, Sites A and B, are connected to two separate and independent real 5G networks, emulating practical scenarios where different network operators or geographical regions are involved. This setup ensures the experiments reflect the complexities of cross-domain and cross-network 5G slicing environments.

Site A and Site B serve as the primary locations for running the main data workloads and hosting the sampling functions for the monitoring process. Specifically, Site A handles the bulk of the computational tasks, including univariate and multivariate Anomaly Detection (AD) modules that detect anomalies across multiple dimensions (e.g., CPU utilization, network bandwidth, latency). These AD modules continuously monitor the system to ensure timely detection of any performance deviations. Site B, in turn, plays a critical role in managing RAN-related tasks. The actual RAN

components are deployed across both Sites A and B, ensuring redundancy and coverage for the 5G-enabled user equipment (UE).

Additionally, all three sites (i.e., A, B, and C) host modules related to Federated Learning (FL) [26]. Site C, in particular, acts as the FL aggregation server, where models trained independently at Sites A and B are periodically sent for aggregation. This federated approach ensures that the privacy of local data is maintained while still enabling the system to learn from multiple sites to improve global performance.

The left part of Figure 3 offers a detailed view of the CPU forecasting MonB5G slice implemented at Site A. In this slice, the UEs are emulated using the *remoteue* mode provided by the Amarisoft Simbox emulator, and the 5G base stations or gNodeBs (gNBs) are realized using Amarisoft Callbox systems. These Callbox systems are responsible not only for emulating the gNBs but also for handling the user plane function (UPF), ensuring seamless data traffic between the UEs and the edge computing resources.

In the following subsections, we cover the experimental implementation of three different *support* slice solutions. These solutions span a spectrum of methods, including proactively initiating actions via the Kubernetes Application Programming Interface (API) to dynamically regulate the compute resources allocated to the Virtual Reality (VR) video streaming server pod. All of these solutions act like pieces of an objective and have a common overarching goal: improving the virtual reality (*umbrella*) network slice performance. Figure 4 illustrates the mapping of the three solutions to the

FIGURE 4. Mapping of network slices to network slice tuples (MS, AD, DE, and ACT) for the VR streaming use case. Sampling functions of the MS are coloured per the corresponding technological domain (RAN and infrastructure in red and orange, respectively).

network slicing tuples (MS, AE, DE, ACT), which together form a higher-level VR streaming slice or tuple.

A. THE USE CASE: VR VIDEO STREAMING

Employing a VR video streaming use case, we explore the challenges and benefits associated with deploying three solutions (considered as different slices) to improve the overall performance of the use case: *i*) FL-based CPU forecasting, *ii*) AD for alarm triggering, and *iii*) multi-agent DRL for RAN bandwidth optimization. For simplicity, specific details of each slice configuration are not provided here, but readers can find further technical breakdowns in [27] and the official YouTube channel.¹ Note that with the introduced network slicing framework, all these solutions are managed by a so-called umbrella slice, as depicted in Figure 4.

In this scenario, the UEs connect to a gNB that provides access to a video streaming server. The server is loaded with highly demanding transcoding workloads to emulate VR processes [26], [28]. Specifically, the server is deployed as a Nginx pod in the Kubernetes cluster of site A (left side of Figure 3) that streams a 4K video transcoded in real-time. We rely on SFs to feed monitoring data from multiple domains (e.g., RAN, Kubernetes nodes, or video server) into the MSs, which passes this data through Prometheus to Grafana to display and trigger alarms. The MSs also feed the AEs, the DEs, and the ACTs, also deployed as pods in the cluster.

B. SLICE 1: FL-BASED CPU FORECASTING

As shown in Figure 3, we deploy a FL-based forecasting slice to predict the CPU utilization of the VR video

¹MonB5G YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCaff8mbiWXPkx3UeLBz3nw>

streaming server to enable proactive scaling operations for ensuring uninterrupted, high-quality service for end users. Measurements of the gNB and the VR video streaming server were performed via the MS to feed the data into the AEs' FL training process, as well as for online inference. Then, the DE and the ACT, which are also deployed as pods in the cluster, preemptively trigger actions via the Kubernetes API to scale up/down the CPU limits of the VR server pod. The same applies to Site B. FL updates between Site A and Site B are performed through the aggregation server at Site C, which aggregates the models of FL-A and FL-B to learn a combined set of VR video streaming user patterns for each site. Finally, whenever the DEs generate a re-scaling decision, the ACTs proactively scale up or down the CPU on the VR video streaming servers to improve the quality of experience of VR video streaming clients while keeping resource efficiency.

During the evaluations, we observed a reduction in communication overhead of more than $\times 11$ compared to the centralized Service Level Agreement (SLA)-constrained algorithm [29]. Accordingly, we noticed an energy reduction of $\times 10$ in the M&O plane, in line with numerical results in [30]. Thus, we corroborate that implementing this solution efficiently keeps a proper user experience in a zero-touch way. Besides, CPU load prediction performance is observed to be similar to the centralized approach – Mean Square Error (MSE) of prediction below 0.1 – while minimizing the need for extensive communication between different components or systems compared to a centralized solution [29]. By distributing the architecture components across multiple sites, we reduce dependency on centralized systems and improve performance and response times. Operational expenditures (OPEX) reduction from service management automation is also achieved by automating network service management through distributed AI and reducing monitoring overhead and energy consumption [28].

C. SLICE 2: ANOMALY DETECTION ALARM TRIGGERING

This solution includes univariate and multivariate ADs, both connected to the MS to collect and analyse metrics for learning and inference purposes. The univariate AD relies on a single input, while the multivariate AD uses multiple inputs. The main goal is to provide alarms to the CPU forecasting solution's DE in case of an anomaly so that the predictor can use additional information beyond the FL model. The implementation of multivariate AD using an intelligent neural network-based algorithm [31] is provided by the distributed framework over Kubernetes. After training the model with the dataset using normal instances across multiple variables, Prometheus and Grafana are used to monitor and visualize the performance of the model. Finally, the trained model is used to detect anomalies in unseen test samples [28], [31]. When the Grafana dashboard is examined, the normalized unseen test sample is displayed, showing CPU usage at the server, average CPU usage at the server, aggregate downlink

bit rate, instantaneous aggregate downlink bit rate at the gNB, and outbound traffic at the server, average outbound traffic flowing from the data interface of the video server.

We found that the first anomaly was detected at the same time step across all variables, which was due to the activation of 8 UEs at a time when only 1 UE was expected in the normal pattern. This resulted in the generation of anomalies in the three variables, with higher-than-expected values in several dimensions, representing multivariate anomalies. For the rest of the time, no anomaly is detected because the data are very similar to the trained ones. By proactively detecting anomalies across the various measures, the overall response time to abnormal behaviour is reduced. The time taken for our gated recurrent units (GRU)-based model for AD purposes is approximately 20.42% faster than LSTM due to faster convergence in training [31]. The proactive detection of anomalies across the multitude of network slice metrics reduces the overall reaction time. Even though numerical results would vary widely depending on system configuration (i.e., sampling rate at different management levels), we observed that proactive detection of anomalous behaviour enables reacting with reconfiguration before a fault occurs.

D. SLICE 3: RADIO RESOURCE ALLOCATION SCENARIO

In the last slice, we address the issue of resource allocation in RAN to show how the above concepts and principles can be integrated into a single design. The goal is to show how the proposed Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) approach can meet the challenging requirements of new services. We target an optimization task in a network slicing context based on extensive experimental studies detailed in [32], [33], and [34]. We ensure the optimal allocation of Physical Resource Blocks (PRBs) in accordance with the SLA. Figure 5 shows the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of the allocation gap for the VR service. The horizontal axis indicates the allocation gap, i.e., the discrepancy between the incoming downlink (DL) traffic and the allocated radio resources in Mbps.

The values on the right side of the vertical dashed purple line (at Allocation Gap 0) indicate underprovisioning, while the values on the left side signal overprovisioning. In the underprovisioning region, the allocated PRB resources are not sufficient to handle the incoming traffic load. This leads to increased latency, lost and dropped packets, or degradation of service quality. On the other hand, the allocated PRBs exceed the actual traffic demand in case of overprovisioning. Although this guarantees that all traffic is served quickly, it can lead to unused and suboptimal use of network resources. The green shaded area shows the percentage of allocation gap values that are in the range of -2 to 2 Mbps. Approximately 92.23% of the total values fall into this range. This range is particularly important because values within this range indicate cases where the allocation gap is minimal, implying a near-optimal allocation of resources, therefore favouring SLA compliance. Let us notice that about 8%

FIGURE 5. CDF of allocation gap for downlink traffic.

FIGURE 6. A subset of experimental KPIs. Radar chart.

deviation from the optimal allocation can be viewed as the initial stages of exploration in the DRL algorithm. As the algorithm refines its policy, the allocation decisions become more precise and efficient.

E. SUMMARY OF EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A summary of the experimental results obtained in the MonB5G project is presented in Figure 6, where we show KPIs comparing MonB5G solutions (with their tuples and slices) against a centralized baseline approach. Using FL, a reduction in signalling/monitoring overhead by more than $\times 11$, an improvement in network energy efficiency by $\times 10$, and an increase in the amount of local processing at two sites are obtained. With DRL, the number of SLA performance violations is reduced by 10%, and the amount of data transmitted to the central management system is reduced by 25%.

Other relevant non-numerical results (or results that vary greatly depending on the scenario) are worth mentioning. In terms of improving network slice performance prediction, FL has achieved similar CPU load prediction performance as centralized prediction; in terms of reducing OPEX by automating the management of services, FL has reduced it by automating the management of network services and DRL by dynamically assigning RAN resources. By proactively detecting anomalies in the multitude of network slice metrics,

the response time (time from identification to resolution through appropriate reconfigurations) to a network slice malfunction has been reduced with AD the method. Regarding convergence time optimization for the distributed/federated AI algorithms, DRL has investigated scalability aspects in the simulation environment [32]. Finally, regarding the generation of accurate and reusable data on the performance of network slices, FL and AD approaches have their corresponding datasets for each scenario are also available in [28].

V. ENVISIONED CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

In this section, we examine forthcoming challenges and prospective avenues within network slicing management. Drawing from our practical insights garnered during collaborative experimentation, we move beyond a purely theoretical perspective and offer a more pragmatic assessment of anticipated challenges and future directions.

Implementing a zero-touch approach to network slice management presents significant challenges. One of the primary concerns is the effective abstraction and exposure of the many network functions involved in a service or application. For example, a gNB can be abstracted as a collection of resources, including bandwidth or PRBs, shared among User Equipments (UEs). However, this abstraction must also account for detailed latency configurations at the MAC scheduler level. Similarly, server infrastructure encompasses cloud-native implementations, such as pods, making it necessary to provide seamless access to these resources, often owned by different actors or providers. Managing resource profiles, influenced by user priority, service requirements, and cost considerations, adds further complexity across diverse hardware, software vendors, and deployment timelines (both RAN and cloud), highlighting the need for more advanced management frameworks.

In this context, it is essential to recognize that end-to-end services, such as VR video streaming over 5G, depend on a variety of factors across the entire infrastructure, from the 5G network to transport and computing systems. Our experimental results confirm that the performance of VR applications depends on more than just 5G Network Functions (NFs); delays in video processing or the selection of an application protocol (e.g., HTTP or RTSP) can create bottlenecks even with high-speed 5G connections. Furthermore, AI/ML models such as FL, AD, and DRL require appropriate network and computing resources, and their convergence speed directly impacts the performance of the overarching network slice. As the ecosystem grows to encompass 6G technologies, this interaction between network slices, AI models, and infrastructure components will become increasingly complex, requiring sophisticated control and management solutions.

A central challenge in this domain is the collection, processing, and analysis of data across various technological domains, particularly as data sources become more diverse and voluminous. To address this, transparent data source

disclosure mechanisms must be established, allowing authenticated users to retrieve real-time metrics or receive updates via push mechanisms. Additionally, determining the parameters to be monitored and identifying appropriate data sources are critical tasks. While the distributed monitoring system we have implemented aids in this process, human intervention remains vital, especially in defining performance-enhancing metrics. To address these challenges, advancements such as Generative AI and digital twins—where LLMs [35] can assist in the automated optimization of network configurations—hold promise for reducing the need for manual intervention and improving the overall efficiency of network operations.

Regarding future directions, the advent of 6G introduces a paradigm shift where LLMs, Generative AI, and advanced edge computing solutions will play an increasingly significant role in automation and network management. LLMs, for instance, can be utilized to automate network slicing configuration, management, and troubleshooting by processing vast amounts of operational data and generating actionable insights in real time. Generative AI can also assist in predicting network behaviour, simulating scenarios for testing purposes, and creating novel models for adaptive resource allocation. In terms of AI/ML model management, continuous monitoring and updating of these models in production environments will be crucial, especially in detecting shifts in data profiles or performance degradation. The scalability of network slicing frameworks will thus depend on AI-driven analysis of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), ensuring that they adapt as the number of slices and network demands grow.

To ensure scalability, it will be critical to evaluate: *i*) whether the time required for slice setup follows a linear or sublinear trend as the number of slices increases, avoiding the super linear scaling problems observed in centralized M&O solutions; *ii*) that AI/ML model performance (e.g., accuracy, loss) is maintained without significant overhead as the system scales, particularly through decentralized architectures that distribute the load across edge and core networks; *iii*) that the number of supported slices scales proportionally with resource allocation, in contrast to centralized systems that may exhibit diminishing returns. Generative AI and LLM-based solutions can further assist in automating these evaluations by dynamically generating and adjusting models to ensure consistent performance and cost efficiency.

Finally, several optimization techniques for FL and other distributed AI systems can improve scalability and performance. These include model pruning, quantization, knowledge distillation, and parameter sharing, all of which can reduce the computational and energy demands of AI/ML systems. As we transition towards B5G and 6G networks, the use of these techniques, combined with the growing capabilities of LLMs and Generative AI, will be vital to ensuring that network slicing systems can efficiently manage the increasing demands placed on them while maintaining high levels of automation and performance.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper has demonstrated the practical application of the MonB5G framework within a real-world 5G cloud-native testbed, specifically targeting a VR video streaming use case. By implementing AI-driven automation and decentralized orchestration, MonB5G effectively addresses the complexities of network slicing management, enabling real-time adaptation to dynamic service demands. The experimental results emphasize the framework's ability to enhance scalability and energy efficiency, particularly in resource-intensive applications. These insights contribute to the broader 6G roadmap by bridging the gap between conceptual designs and practical deployments, providing a foundation for future advancements in network slice management.

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